

Life Cycle Assessment of Mumbai Trans Harbour Link

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Abstract— The Mumbai Trans Harbour Link (MTHL) is a monumental infrastructure project set to transform transportation connectivity in the Mumbai Metropolitan Region. The 21.8km long sea bridge is of strategic importance, connecting south Mumbai to Navi Mumbai. Even though construction has potential environmental impacts, the construction of a project can't be avoided. The areas of impact are habitats living nearby, greenhouse gas emissions, the atmosphere, resource consumption, waste generation, etc. This impact has led to the need for a life cycle assessment of the project to assess various environmental impacts throughout its life cycle & identify areas of improvement suggest alternatives to mitigate those impacts and provide suggestions for sustainable design and construction. This study presents a comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA) of the MTHL, assessing its environmental impacts throughout its life cycle. Through a rigorous analysis, the research delves into the planning, material preparation, construction, and operation phases of the MTHL. The assessment covers direct and indirect emissions, providing a holistic view of the carbon footprint associated with this large-scale infrastructure project. The results provide crucial insights for policymakers, engineers, and environmental planners aiming to minimize the environmental impact of large infrastructure projects. This research underscores the importance of integrating sustainability considerations throughout the project lifecycle to achieve long-term environmental benefits.

Keywords— CO₂, Energy Consumption, Greenhouse Gas, Impact Assessment, Life Cycle Impact Assessment, MMDRA, MTHL, Sustainable Practices.

I. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry wields substantial influence in India, significantly contributing to the nation's GDP. However, its growth and practices also come with various environmental impacts with wide-ranging consequences. Here, we delve into the facts and figures surrounding the construction industry's environmental impact, and its influence on various environmental factors. The construction industry in India consumes nearly 40% of the country's total energy and is responsible for approximately 25% of its water consumption. (source: Energy and Resources Institute (TERI), India). These numbers highlight the sector's significant demand for resources, contributing to resource depletion and environmental strain. Construction activities, from transportation to the use of energy-intensive materials, contribute to significant greenhouse gas emissions. Addressing emissions is vital to combat climate change. Also, the construction process demands substantial energy for activities such as manufacturing construction materials, transportation, and on-site operations. This can result in high greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to climate change. To mitigate these environmental impacts, the construction industry is increasingly focusing on sustainable and eco-friendly construction practices.

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) helps mitigate environmental impacts by identifying critical areas, informing decision-making, optimizing processes, promoting eco-friendly materials, reducing energy use, minimizing waste, addressing pollution sources, managing carbon footprints, guiding sustainable product design, ensuring regulatory compliance, and engaging stakeholders in sustainable practices. LCA supports organizations in making informed choices that reduce environmental burdens and promote sustainability.

II. HIGHLIGHTS OF THE MTHL BRIDGE

A) Length, lane, width

TABLE I
DESCRIPTION OF MTHL BRIDGE

1	Length of bridge	The total length is about 21.8 km. That's it. (Sea length about 16.5 km and land length about 5.5 km)
2	The width of the bridge	30.1 m (3+3 lane)
3	ROW	Total of 120 m.
4	Lane	6-lane bridge (3+3 lane and 2 Emergency lanes)
5	Vehicle speed proposed	100 km / h
6	Railway over bridge	2 (at Kharkopar and Vasai in Navi Mumbai)
7	The structure of the bridge	Concrete Segment slabs up to 60 m in span length are used for the project. Longer spans are being constructed for the first time in India using steel, Orthotropic Steel Deck (OSD) type technology.
8	Proposed Interchanges	1. Interchange at Sewri consists of 8 ramps. 2 ramps connecting Haji Bandar Road, 4 ramps connecting Mumbai and Navi Mumbai to Eastern Expressway, and 2 ramps connecting the Sewri-Worli connector. 2. There are 6 ramps in Shivajinagar interchange for connecting CIDCO's proposed coastal road.

B) Project outline map

Fig. 1 MTHL map

C) Site location

Fig. 2 Satellite image of MTHL

- Sewri End:
Latitude - 18°59'48"
Longitude - 72°52'21"
- Chirle End:
Latitude - 18°56'18"
Longitude - 73°01'54"

TABLE II
TOPOGRAPHY AND GEOGRAPHY OF THE SITE

Section	Topographic Classification	Depth of the sea	Topographic feature
Section -1 0-0.72km	Land (partially tidal area)	-	Flat
Section-2 0.72-5.06km	Tidal Area	0.0m- 3m	Flat (Partially mangrove area)
Section-3 5.60-10.75km	Sea Area	4.5m- 7m	Deepest area in the sea along the alignment
Section-4	Sea area (Partially tidal area)	0.0-4 m	Flat (Partially mangrove area)
Section-5 16.75-21.84km	Land	-	Hill and rock mountainous area (Basaltic layer)

D) Seismic Zone

The following figure shows the project lies in Seismic Zone III, which is of Moderate risk zone.

Fig. 3 Seismic Zone in India

III. INTRODUCTION TO LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT

The construction industry has a major share in the Indian economy. According to recent surveys, the construction market reached more than 8% of the country's GDP out of which a substantial amount is spent on infrastructure development, but sustainability implementation in this sector remains understudied. As the environmental impacts caused by buildings and bridge construction have become more extensive, new studies and strategies have been developed to find more efficient solutions in the construction industry. Therefore, the life cycle assessment LCA has been introduced to provide a more detailed overview of the

environmental impacts because the LCA considers different life stages throughout a material's whole life cycle. The following figure shows the construction industry stands for 11% of global energy-related CO₂ emissions. United Nations regarded the sustainable development goals SDGs as objectives of sustainable solutions in infrastructure design.

Fig. 4 Global CO₂ emissions by sector adapted from (UN, 2017)

LCA is a systematic method for quantifying the potential environmental impacts of a product, asset, or service throughout its whole life cycle, from raw material acquisition, through manufacture, use, and maintenance until the end of its life. The potential environmental categories include resource depletion, human health, and ecological health (ISO 14040, 2006). The LCA process can be used to determine the potential environmental impacts of any product, process, or service. The application of LCA can provide scientifically based results for decision-makers, thus helping efforts to set new criteria for environmentally friendly design, compare and choose environmentally competitive products, and identify environmental deficiencies of a product for further optimization. As stated in the ISO LCA standards, the general LCA framework consists of the following four phases:

[1] Goal and Scope Definition:

In this initial phase, the objectives and boundaries of the LCA study are established. This includes defining the purpose of the assessment, the system boundaries (e.g., cradle-to-grave, cradle-to-gate), the functional unit (what the product or process is meant to achieve), and the intended audience of the study. The goal and scope definition phase helps clarify the specific questions the LCA is intended to answer.

[2] Inventory analysis:

In this phase, a comprehensive inventory of all inputs (e.g., raw materials, energy, water) and outputs (e.g., emissions, waste) associated with the product, process, or activity is compiled. Data on resource consumption, transportation, and other relevant factors are collected and analyzed. This phase helps in quantifying the environmental inputs and outputs at each stage of the life cycle.

[3] Impact assessment:

Data collected in the previous phase is used in the LCIA phase to assess the potential environmental impacts. Impact categories are established, which can include climate change, acidification, eutrophication, resource depletion, and more. Various impact assessment methods are used to quantify the effects on each category, and these can be measured in different units, such as carbon dioxide equivalents for climate change.

[4] Interpretation:

In this phase, the results of the LCIA are evaluated and interpreted about the defined goals and scope of the study. The goal is to provide a clear understanding of the environmental impacts and identify hotspots, critical stages in the life cycle, and potential areas for improvement. Sensitivity analysis may also be performed to assess the robustness of the results.

Fig. 5 Framework of Life cycle assessment

IV. DATA COLLECTION

The data collection process focused on capturing detailed information across all phases of the bridge’s life cycle, including raw material extraction, construction, operation, maintenance, and decommissioning. Each phase required specific data types, collected through a combination of primary and secondary sources. Primary data was obtained directly from project stakeholders, including construction companies, materials used, resources, and methodology applied. Secondary data was sourced from existing literature, government reports, and databases related to construction industry standards and environmental impact assessments.

- Below is the breakdown of the quantity of materials used sourced from the JICA project report.

TABLE III
QUANTITY OF MATERIALS (FOUNDATION PILE)

Diameter of piles In mm	Number of piles (A)	Number of piles per pier (B)	Average length per pile (m) (C)	Total pile length (m) = A x B x C
1000	14	8	17.848	1,999
1200	174	4	18.869	13,133
1500	34	2	19.397	1,319
2000	319	4	28.120	35,881
2400	44	4	28.864	5,080
				57,412

- Pile diameter according to the preliminary design: 100/1200/1500 mm (sewri IC) and 2000/2400 (marine area).

TABLE IV
QUANTITY OF MATERIALS (SUBSTRUCTURE)

Number of piers (A)	Average concrete volume/ pier (m3) (B)	Total concrete volume (m3) =A x B
585	302.309	176,851

TABLE V
QUANTITY OF MATERIALS (SUPERSTRUCTURE-CONCRETE)

Bridge length of concrete(m) (A)	Average area of cross-section (m ²) (B)	Number of bridges (C)	Total concrete volume (m ³) = A x B x C	
7,552	12.175	2	183,885	Main Alignment
6,441	8.079	1	52,035	Ramps
			235,920	

TABLE VI
QUANTITY OF MATERIALS (SUPERSTRUCTURE-STEEL BOX GIRDER BRIDGE)

Bridge length of steel (m) (A)	Average weight of steel (kg/m) (B)	Number of bridges (C)	Total steel weight (kg) = A x B x C	
2,333	12,600	2	58,792,000	Main Alignment

- There are 2 bridges in the main alignment: the inbound lane (Chirle to Sewri) and the outbound lane (Sewri to Chirle).

Pavement length along the bridge (A)	Average pavement width (m) (B)	Layers (C)	Total pavement area (m ²) = A x B x C
16,326	23.016	2	751,526

- A – Total pavement length including main alignment and ramps.
- B – Average pavement width including main alignment and ramps.
- C – The pavement shall be executed in 2 layers.

TABLE VII
QUANTITY OF MATERIALS (NOISE BARRIER)

Noise Barrier Length along bridge (m) (A)	Barrier Height (m)	Number of Noise Barrier (C)	Total Noise Barrier Area (m ²)
1,700	2	2	6,800

TABLE VIII
QUANTITY OF MATERIALS (CONCRETE BARRIER)

Concrete Barrier length along bridge (m) (A)	The average number of concrete barriers. (B)	Total concrete barrier length (m) = A x B
16,326	3.21	52,422

- B- The number shown is an average considering 4 barriers in the main alignment and 2 barriers in the ramps.

V. LIFE CYCLE CALCULATION MODEL

This study establishes a carbon emission calculation model based on the whole life cycle evaluation combined with the carbon emission coefficient method to calculate the carbon footprint for each stage of the life cycle of the Mumbai trans harbour link project.

A) Calculation Boundary

The Mumbai Trans Harbour Link (MTHL) is one of India's most ambitious infrastructure projects, connecting Mumbai with its satellite city, Navi Mumbai. Conducting a lifecycle assessment (LCA) of such a project is essential to understand its environmental impacts across various stages, from planning to demolition. Let's delve into each phase in detail:

[1] Planning and design phase

- During this stage, engineers and planners evaluate various alignment options, considering factors like environmental impact, cost, and feasibility.
- LCA begins here with an assessment of the environmental impacts of various uses of appliances. This phase is associated with the use of various use of appliances that cause the burning of fossil fuel for energy consumption which eventually leads to carbon emissions to the environment.

[2] Material preparation stage

- This phase involves sourcing raw materials for construction, including steel, concrete, and aggregate.
- LCA during this stage evaluates the environmental impact of extracting, processing, and transporting these materials.

- It assesses energy consumption, greenhouse gas emissions, and waste generation associated with material production.
- [3] Construction Phase
- Construction begins with site preparation, followed by foundation work and structural erection.
 - LCA focuses on energy consumption, emissions, and waste generation during construction.
 - Operation of a temporary facility at the site, for example, Site office, containers, security guard cabins, and labour camp. All the units are responsible for energy consumption which causes fossil fuel burning which eventually leads to greenhouse gas emission.
- [4] Operation and maintenance
- Once the MTHL is operational, it enters this phase where it's used for daily transportation and requires regular maintenance.
 - LCA assesses the energy consumption and emissions associated with operating the bridge, including vehicle traffic and lighting.

VI. INVENTORY ANALYSIS

A) Formulas:

1. Formula for calculating carbon emissions in the planning and design phase.

$$C_{GH} = \sum_{i=1}^n E_{gh,i} F_i$$

where,

- C_{GH} is the overall amount of carbon emission in the planning and designing phase in kgCO₂e0.
- $E_{gh,i}$ is the entire usage of the i^{th} energy source in the planning and design phase (kWh or kg).
- F_i depicts the carbon emission factor of the i^{th} energy source in kgCO₂e/kg.

2. Formula for calculating carbon emissions for the building materials preparation stage.

$$C_{SC} = \sum_{i=1}^n M_i F_i$$

where,

- C_{SC} is the carbon emission of the production stage of building materials in kgCO₂e.
- M_i is the consumption of the i^{th} main building material.
- F_i is the carbon emission factor of the i^{th} main building material in kgCO₂e/unit quantity of building material.

3. Formula for calculating carbon emissions for the construction phase.

$$C_{JZ} = C_{sg} + C_{ls}$$

where,

- C_{JZ} is the overall carbon emission during the construction stage in kgCO₂e.
- C_{sg} is the carbon emission of construction machinery throughout construction in kgCO₂e.
- C_{ls} is the carbon emission throughout the operation of the temporary facility in kgCO₂e.

$$1) C_{sg} = \sum_{i=1}^n C_{B,i} n_i$$

- C_{sg} is the carbon emission of construction machinery in kgCO₂e.
- $C_{B,i}$ is the carbon emission factor of the i^{th} type of construction machinery in kgCO₂e/shift, it can be acquired by multiplying the energy use of each shift of machinery by the corresponding carbon emission factor.

$$2) C_{ls} = \sum_{i=1}^n E_{ls,i} F_i$$

- C_{1s} is the entire amount of carbon emission during the operation of a temporary facility in $kgCO_2e$.
- $E_{1s,i}$ is the total amount of energy consumption during the operation of a temporary facility in kWh.
- F_i is the carbon emission factor of the i^{th} energy source in $kgCO_2e/kWh$.

4. Formula for calculating carbon emissions for the operation and maintenance phase.

$$C_{op} = \sum_{i=1}^n D_t F_i$$

where,

- C_{op} is the entire amount of carbon emission during the operation phase in $kgCO_2e$.
- $E_{1s,i}$ is the total distance traveled in km.
- F_i is the carbon emission factor of the i^{th} energy source in $kgCO_2e/km$.

B) Calculation:

1. **Planning and design phase.**

TABLE IX
ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF APPLIANCES

Appliance	Watt	Time in (hrs.)	No.	kWh/day	kWh/yr.
Ac	60	8	6	2.88	1051.2
Led light	20	8	10	1.6	584
Fan	60	8	8	3.84	1401.6
Pc	200	8	20	32	11680
Printer	30	2	4	0.24	87.6
Xerox machine	550	2	4	4.4	1606
Telephone	3	3	5	0.045	16.425
Projector	230	2	1	0.46	167.9
Water cooler	110	2	1	0.22	80.3
				Total = 16675.025 kWh/yr	

TABLE X
CARBON EMISSION FACTOR

Total Energy consumption	Carbon emission factor	Carbon emissions per year
16675.025 kWh/yr.	0.7082 $kgCO_2e$	11839.27 $kgCO_2e/yr.$

TABLE XI
CARBON EMISSION OVER THE YEARS

Assuming 3% as incremental rate of CO_2 emission over 6 years	
YEARS	KG OF CO_2e
0	11839.27
1	12194.44578
2	12560.27916
3	12937.08753
4	13325.20016
5	13724.95616
6	14136.70485
Total	90.717×10^3
For 4 Office	362.868×10^3

2. Material Preparation Stage

1. Production Phase

- a) Concrete- M55 is used dominantly, Following is the data regarding the quantity of concrete used in different members.

TABLE XII
QUANTITY OF MATERIAL (CONCRETE)

Concrete used in Piles	1,54,458 m3
Concrete used in main alignment	1,83,885 m3
Concrete used in ramps	52,035 m3
Concrete used in the concrete barrier	16,573 m3
Total Volume of concrete used	5,83,802 m3

- Total Volume of concrete used = 5,83,802 m³
- kgCO_{2e} Emitted = Mi Fi = 5,83,802 x 252.9 = **14,76,43,526 kgCO_{2e}** (Emission factor of concrete is 252.9 kgCO_{2e}).

b) Steel

TABLE XIII
QUANTITY OF MATERIAL (STEEL)

The steel used in Pier	7,075 m ³ .
Steel used in Pile	6,180.28 m ³ .
Stell used in Superstructure	7,490 m ³ .
Total Steel used	20,745.28 m ³ .
Total steel used in kg	16,28,50,448 kg.

- kgCO_{2e} Emitted = Mi Fi = 16,28,50,448 x 2.03 = 33,05,86,409.4 kgCO_{2e} (Emission factor of steel = 2.03 kgCO_{2e})

c) Layers on Bridge Deck

1. Waterproofing layer = 40mm thickness
2. Stone mastic asphalt (protective layer) and another asphalt layer = 80mm thickness.
Total Pavement Area = 7,51,526 m²

TABLE XIV
AMOUNT OF BITUMEN

Amount of waterproofing material used (m ³)	Density of bitumen	Weight of bitumen
7,51,526 x 0.04= 30,062 m ³	1,050 kg/m ³	3,15,65,100 kg

- kgCO_{2e} emitted= 3,15,65,100 x 0.222= 70,07,453 kgCO_{2e}. (Emission factor of bitumen = 0.222kgCO_{2e}/kg).

TABLE XV
AMOUNT OF ASPHALT

Amount of asphalt used	Density of asphalt	Weight
7,51,526 x 0.08= 60,123 m ³	2,400 kg/m ³	1,44,295.2 x 10 ³ kg

- kgCO_{2e} emitted= 1,44,295.2 x 103 x 0.07115= 1,02,66,604 kgCO_{2e} (Emission factor of asphalt = 0.07115 kgCO_{2e}/kg).

d) Noise barrier

TABLE XVI
AMOUNT OF ALUMINUM NOISE BARRIER

Area	6800 m ²
Thickness	0.1m
Volume	6,800 x 0.1 = 680 m ³
Density of Aluminium	2,710 kg/m ³
Weight	2,710 x 680 = 18,42,800 kg

2. Transportation of material to the site after preparation

TABLE XVII
CARBON EMISSION DUE TO TRANSPORTATION OF MATERIAL

Material	Volume	Transportation distance	CO ₂ Emission factor	Total
Steel	20,745.28 m ³	4 km	19.6 kgCO ₂ e/10 ² t.k m	16264.29 kgCO ₂ e
Concrete	3,31,309 m ³	1.5 km		97404.85 kgCO ₂ e
Pavement material: 1) Asphalt 2) Waterproofing -Total	90,184.08 m ³ 60,122.08 m ³ 30,062 m ³	5 km		88380.4 kgCO ₂ e
Noise barrier	680 m ³	5 km		666.4 kgCO ₂ e
Miscellaneous	22,145 m ³	5 km		21702.1 kgCO ₂ e
				224418.04 KgCO₂e

3. Construction phase.

a) Emission due to energy consumption of temporary facility at Sewri end.

TABLE XVIII
SITE OFFICE AT SEWRI END

Appliance	Watt	Time In (Hrs.)	No.	kWh/Day	kWh/Yr.
Ac	60	8	30	14.4	5256
Led Light	20	12	40	9.6	3504
Fan	60	12	30	21.6	7884
Pc	200	8	30	48	17520
Printer	30	5	5	0.75	273.75
Xerox Machine	550	5	5	13.75	5018.75
Telephone	3	5	5	0.075	27.375
Projector	230	4	2	1.84	671.6
Water Cooler	110	6	4	2.64	963.6
			Total		41,119.075 kWh/yr.

TABLE XIX
ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF TEMPORARY FACILITY (2 CONTAINERS)

Appliance	Watt	Time in (hrs.)	No.	kWh/day	kWh/yr
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Led light	20	8	6	0.96	350.4
Fan	60	8	8	3.84	1401.6
Pc	200	8	4	6.4	2336
Printer	30	3	4	0.36	131.4
Xerox machine	550	2	2	2.2	803
Telephone	3	2	2	0.012	4.38
Water cooler	110	6	4	2.64	963.6
			Total	5990.38 kWh/yr	

TABLE XX
ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF TEMPORARY FACILITY (2 SECURITY GUARD CABINS)

Appliance	Watt	Time in (hrs.)	No.	kWh/day	kWh/yr
Led Light	20	24	4	1.92	700.8
Fan	60	24	4	5.76	2102.4
				Total = 2803.2 kWh/yr.	

TABLE XXI
ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF TEMPORARY FACILITY (2 LABOR CAMPS)

Appliance	Watt	Time in (hrs.)	No.	kWh/day	kWh/yr
Led Light	20	24	70	33.6	12264
Fan	60	24	80	115.2	42048
				Total = 54312 kWh/yr.	

TABLE XXII
ENERGY SOURCE OF ELECTRICITY PRODUCTION

Energy Source	Contribution in TPP%	CO ₂ Factor (kg CO ₂ / kWh)	Energy consumption (kWh)	Kg of CO ₂ /yr.
Coal	0.75	1.1	104224.655	85985.34038
Natural Gas	0.15	0.5	104224.655	7816.849125
Oil	0.1	0.9	104224.655	9380.21895
			Total	103182.40

TABLE XXIII
ASSUMING 10% AS THE INCREMENTAL RATE OF CO₂ EMISSION OVER 6 YEARS

Years	Kg OF CO ₂	Kg of CO _{2e}
0	103182.41	3074835.77
1	113500.65	3382319.35
2	137335.79	4092606.41
3	182793.93	5447259.14
4	267628.59	7975332.09
5	431018.53	12844352.1
Total	1235459.89	36816704.87

b) Energy consumption of temporary facility at Chirle end.

TABLE XXIV
SITE OFFICE AT CHIRLE END

Appliance	Watt	Time in (hrs.)	No.	kWh/day	kWh/yr.
Ac	60	12	45	32.4	11826
Led light	20	12	50	12	4380
Fan	60	12	60	43.2	15768
Pc	200	12	50	120	43800
Printer	30	6	8	1.44	525.6
Xerox machine	550	6	10	33	12045
Telephone	3	5	8	0.12	43.8
Projector	230	5	4	4.6	1679
Water cooler	110	8	6	5.28	1927.2
					Total = 91994.6

TABLE XXV
ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF TEMPORARY FACILITY (2 SECURITY GUARD CABINS)

Appliance	Watt	Time in (hrs.)	No.	kWh/day	kWh/yr
Led light	20	24	4	1.92	700.8
Fan	60	24	4	5.76	2102.4
					Total = 2803.2

TABLE XXVI
ENERGY CONSUMPTION OF TEMPORARY FACILITY (2 LABOR CAMPS)

Appliance	Watt	Time in (hrs.)	No.	kWh/day	kWh/yr
Led light	20	24	100	48	17520
Fan	60	24	120	172.8	63072
					Total = 80592

TABLE XXVII
ENERGY SOURCE OF ELECTRICITY PRODUCTION

Energy Source	Contribution in TPP%	CO ₂ Factor (kg CO ₂ / kWh)	Energy consumption (kWh)	Kg of CO ₂ /yr
Coal	0.75	1.1	181781.68	149969.886
Natural Gas	0.15	0.5	181781.68	13633.626
Oil	0.1	0.9	181781.68	16360.3512
				Total = 179963.8632

TABLE XXVIII
ASSUMING 10% AS THE INCREMENTAL RATE OF CO₂ EMISSION OVER 5 YEARS

Years	Kg of CO ₂	Kg of CO ₂ e
0	179963.86	5362923.12
1	197960.25	5899215.44
2	239531.90	7138050.68
3	318816.96	9500745.45
4	466779.91	13910041.42
5	751753.72	22402260.8
TOTAL	2154806.61	64213236.9

c) Emission due to use of construction machinery

TABLE XXIX
MACHINE USED AND IT'S CARBON EMISSIONS

Construction Machinery Used	Emission Factor	Shift (Active hour & Volume)	Carbon emissions
A) Substructure Equipment			
1. Pilling Rig	1862 KgCO ₂ e/Shift	212	3,94,744
2. Back Hoe	181.94 KgCO ₂ e/Shift	124	22,560.56
3. Concrete pump	0.74 KgCO ₂ e/m ³	3,31,309 m ³	2,45,168.66
4. Floating Crane	496 KgCO ₂ e/Shift	396	1,96,416
5. Vibration Compactor	0.04 KgCO ₂ e/m ³	3,31,309 m ³	13,252.36
B) Superstructure equipment			
1. Road Roller	2.24 KgCO ₂ e/Shift	88	197.12
2. Asphalt Paver	858 KgCO ₂ e/Shift	88	75,504
3. Bridge Girder erection machine	992 KgCO ₂ e/Shift	660	6,54,720
4. Dump Truck	1392 KgCO ₂ e/Shift	66	91,872
			Total = 16,94,434.7

4. Operation Stage

TABLE XXX
PROJECTED TRAFFIC VIA MTHL OVER THE PERIOD OF 10 YEARS

Year	Car	LCV	Bus	HCV	MAV
2021	36250	2028	2700	7550	1975
2022	37700	2109	2808	7852	2054
2023	39208	2193	2920	8166	2136
2024	40776	2281	3037	8493	2222
2025	42407	2372	3159	8832	2310
2026	44104	2467	3285	9186	2403
2027	45868	2566	3416	9553	2499
2028	47703	2669	3553	9935	2599
2029	49611	2775	3695	10333	2703
2030	51595	2886	3843	10746	2811

TABLE XXXI
CARBON EMISSION PER DAY IN THE YEAR 2024

Vehicle	Factor (kg/km)	Daily traffic	Kilometres driven	Distance travelled (Km)	CO ₂ emission (kg)
Car	0.25	40776	21.8	888916.8	222229.2
LCV	0.143	10180	21.8	221924	31735.13
Bus	0.0151	3037	21.8	66206.6	999.72
HCV	0.5	8492	21.8	185125.6	92562.8
MAV	0.5	2221	21.8	48417.8	24208.9
					Total = 371735.75

TABLE XXXII
CARBON EMISSION PER DAY OVER THE YEARS

Year	CO ₂ emission in KgCO ₂ e
2024	371735.75
2025	386640.11
2026	402093.95
2027	418194.47
2028	434910.99
2029	452293.26
2030	470384.99
2031	489200.391

VII. RESULTS

A) *Planning and design stage*

- In the planning and design phase, the carbon emission increased exponentially over the year. This stage started in the year 2012 and was completed in the year 2018. It includes energy consumption of various appliances used when stakeholders, consultants, and project managers conducted feasibility studies, prepared project reports, undertook surveys, and various other activities. The carbon footprint left in this stage due to energy consumption is calculated.

Fig. 6 CO₂ uptake over the years

B) *Material preparation stage*

a) *Production stage*

- In the material preparation stage the raw material is first extracted from the environment followed by the preparation of the finished product from the extracted raw material which has undergone various manufacturing processes and after all transportation of construction material to the site. All these processes are responsible for emissions to the environment. The carbon emission associated with all the processes is evaluated.

Fig. 7 Emission during production of construction material

b) Transportation stage

Fig. 8 Emission during transportation material to the site

c) Construction stage

a) Emission due to use of construction machinery

Fig. 9 Emission due to use of construction machinery (Substructure)

- The use of construction machinery during the construction phase accounts for a large amount of carbon emission. Most of the equipment is operated via fuels like petrol, and diesel. etc. Burning of this fuel causes the emission of greenhouse gases to the environment. Those emissions are taken into account and measured. Common engineering equipment that was used at the Mumbai trans harbour link project are gantry cranes floating cranes, rebar hydraulic tensioning equipment, piling rig, backhoe, vibration compactor, etc.

Fig. 10 Emission due to use of construction machinery (Superstructure)

b) Emission due to operation of temporary facility

Fig. 11 CO₂ uptake from temporary facility at Sewri end

Fig. 12 CO₂ uptake from temporary facility at Chirle end

- During the operation of temporary facilities at a construction site of MTHL, emissions primarily result from energy consumption, transportation, and waste management. Energy use, often from diesel generators or grid electricity, leads to CO₂ emissions. Transportation of materials and personnel generates emissions from vehicles.
- The components of the temporary facility included, a site office, security guard cabin, labour camps, etc. The energy consumption due to the use of various appliances in these components results in emissions to the environment.

- Also, the movement of traffic on the site causes the burning of fossil fuel which eventually leads to CO₂ uptake. So, these emissions are measures considering the temporary facility arrangement made at the site.
- Emissions from a casting yard primarily arise from energy use, transportation, and waste management. Energy consumption, often from fossil fuels, leads to CO₂ emissions. Transportation of materials and products to and from the yard generates emissions from vehicles.
- As the project is being built on a large scale, the girders were being manufactured on the site itself. The production of girders and various other materials needs the operation of machinery and advanced equipment. The use of these machinery causes the burning of fossil fuels and leads to greenhouse gas emissions. So, the casting yard on site is analyzed, which machines were used are evaluated and accordingly, the CO₂ emission is measured.

Fig. 13 Emission due to use of machineries in casting yard

D) Operation stage

- In the operation stage the emission will be mainly due to the movement of vehicles. The bridge is to be designed for a period of over 100 years.
- So, the forecast of vehicles traveling daily through the MTHL bridge is identified over a period of one decade.
- Also, various other factors contribute to the emissions during the operation stage such as the operation of temporary facilities at the bridge, for example, the Toll Plaza, street lights, and emissions caused due to the maintenance process of the 21.8 km long span Seabridge.
- Due to lack of data availability only the emission due to the movement of vehicles via MTHL is evaluated for a period of one decade.

Fig. 14 Carbon emission per day per year

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

- The calculated carbon emission for the Mumbai Trans Harbour Link serves as a reminder of carbon footprints associated with large-scale infrastructure projects.
- With meticulous analysis and calculation, it becomes evident that the MTHL's construction and operation contribute significantly to greenhouse gas emissions, amplifying concerns about climate change and environmental sustainability.
- These findings underscore the urgent need for proactive measures to mitigate the carbon footprint of the MTHL and similar projects.
- From the outset, prioritizing the use of low-carbon materials, implementing energy-efficient construction practices, and optimizing transportation logistics can significantly reduce emissions during the construction phase.
- Furthermore, integrating renewable energy sources into the operation of the bridge and promoting sustainable transportation modes can further curb carbon emissions over the project's lifespan.
- In conclusion, while the carbon emissions associated with the MTHL bridge present a significant challenge, they also represent an opportunity for innovation and transformation.

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